

HYPOGLYCEMIC AND ANTI-HYPERGLYCEMIC STUDY OF A POWDER COMBINATION FROM THREE LOCAL PLANTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hyperglycemia is defined as blood glucose > 140 mg/dl, and treatment is recommended when glucose levels are persistently > 140–180 mg/dl. Conventional therapies, including metformin, sulfonylureas, and insulin, have long served as the cornerstone of treatment. However, they often face limitations, such as adverse effects, reduced efficacy over time, The World Health Organization (WHO) has been playing a major role in the promotion of traditional medicine. This study aims to investigate the effect of a tri therapy of some local herbal resources (*Allium sativum*, *Zingiber officinale* and *Hibiscus rosa sinensis*), known for their anti hyperglycemic effects on glycemic control in laboratory rats. **Materials and Methods:** The plant materials for the study obtained from various sources were dried and crushed to powder then extracted in ethanol. This extract was concentrated and dried after which we obtained a fine powder to be used for diabetic control. The rats used in this study were reared in the animal laboratory. During the study, the rats were separated into six

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different groups each of which received 2g of glucose solution orally after monitoring their BGLs using the IVD glucose meter, followed by various substances per group (4 mg, 10 mg and 40 mg of powder combination, glimepiride² and distilled water). The blood glucose levels of the rats in each group were taken at T0, T30, T60 and T90. The data obtained was analyzed using GraphPad Prism 8. **Results:** About 50 g of powder was obtained after drying the concentrated extract. The results of the analysis showed highly significant differences between the different groups at different times following the turkey multiple comparison test with p value 0.0034 between Group B (glimepiride²) and group E (powder at 40mg) , 0.0008 between group D (powder at 10mg) and E at T30. T30 being the focal point as the highest peaks of BGLs appeared at T30. **Conclusion:** The statistical analysis revealed the positive control (glimepiride²) to be the most active in glucose control. Powder combinations at 4mg and 10mg showed sharp peaks of hyperglycemia at T30 compared to other groups. The powder combination at 40mg showed normal glucose values but slightly high compared to the positive control. Thus the anti-hyperglycemic property of the powder combination was dose dependent, with 40mg being the most active relative to the other concentrations.

KEYWORDS: Anti-hyperglycemic property, Hyperglycemic control, Glimepiride².

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperglycemia is defined as blood glucose > 140 mg/dl, and treatment is recommended when glucose levels are persistently > 140–180 mg/dl.^[1] is a common effect of uncontrolled diabetes and over time leads to serious damage to many of the body's systems.^[2] Observational studies demonstrating that elevated blood glucose is associated with morbidity and mortality in hospitalized patients.^[3] Hyperglycemia is the technical term for high blood glucose (blood sugar). High blood glucose happens when the body has too little insulin or when the body can't use insulin properly^[4], In some cases, an endocrine disease can be associated with glucose intolerance or diabetes mellitus((prolonged hyperglycemia), and the latter can falsely be considered as type 2 diabetes(High blood sugar). Glycemic imbalance can be a direct or indirect consequence of excessive hormone production. Endocrine diseases such as acromegaly, Cushing's syndrome and pheochromocytoma can increase glucose production and cause insulin resistance. Hyperthyroidism, hyperaldosteronism, glucagonoma and somatostatinoma lead to hyperglycemia by other physiopathological mechanisms more to that, impairment of glucose metabolism is commonly encountered in Cushing's syndrome.^[5] It is the source of significant morbidity and mortality even after successful treatment of

Cushing's.^[6] Stress and infections are also listed amongst the underlying causes of this condition.^[7,8]

Hyperglycemia is among the most widespread non-communicable diseases and poses a substantial global health challenge.^[9] In 2022, 14% of adults aged 18 years and older were living with diabetes, an increase from 7% in 1990. More than half (59%) of adults aged 30 years and over living with diabetes were not taking medication for their diabetes in 2022. Diabetes treatment coverage was lowest in low- and middle-income countries.^[2]

Conventional therapies, including metformin, sulfonylureas, and insulin, have long served as the cornerstone of treatment. However, they often face limitations, such as adverse effects, reduced efficacy over time.

Medicinal plants and their preparations have been used since the earliest history of mankind, and they have formed one of the foundations for healthcare in virtually all cultures throughout the world. The use of herbal remedies is an integral part of traditional medicine, which is practiced in different forms in Cameroon as well as in other regions of the world. In spite of their long tradition of use as medicinal products, the public's interest in herbal remedies is still growing with particular emphasis on their clinical, pharmaceutical and economic value. A significant shift has occurred from the use of orthodox medicines to herbal medicinal products globally, and this trend is similarly observed in Cameroon. In many rural communities in Cameroon and other developing countries, the use of herbal remedies forms an important component of primary healthcare, and in some cases, it is the only accessible healthcare.

In recognition of this fact, over the years, the World Health Organization (WHO) has been playing a major role in the promotion of traditional medicine. Accordingly, the WHO resolution WHA42.43 of 1989 urged member states to introduce measures for the regulation and control of medicinal plant products and for the establishment and maintenance of suitable standards.^[10] Amongst thousands of the plants to display biological activity is *Hibiscus* spp^[11], Ginger and garlics known to treat many conditions amongst which, hyperglycemia.^[12,13] These plants are local resources and with the help of studies like this they can be transform to potential drugs that can be used in our society. These resources have not yet been fully exploited for their hypoglycemic properties, especially in this part of the

world. This study is meant to investigate the outcome of a powder combination from *Allium sativum*, *Zingiber officinale* and *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* on glycemc control.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

II.1. Materials

Plant material

The plants were identified at the national herbarium by a botanist in the capital city Yaounde, With voucher number. Biological materials used during the study were:

Hibiscus rosa sinensis flower harvested on Faculty of Medicine and Pharmaceutical Sciences campus within the month February and identified under the number 3386/SRFCam:

Zingiber officinale (43144/HNC) bought from the market:

Allium sativum (44818/HNC) bought from the market.

Zingiber officinale and *Allium sativum* were collected from the period of February 15th till March 1st, our materials were being transformed into their final evaluable forms for various testing and assessments.

Animal material

Wistar rats reared in the animal lab on Faculty of Medicine and Pharmaceutical Sciences.

II.2. Methods

II.2.1. Transformation of the plant materials

The following steps were taken during the transformation course; The ginger, garlic and hibiscus flower leaves followed the same path:

Figure 1: Steps Taken To Transform The Plant Materials.^[11,12]

II.2.2. Formulation of final powder

The final powder was obtained by mixing the individual powders in an average effective proportions from the different review articles.

II.2.3. Acute toxicity test

In this section of our studies, on the day prior to the evaluation, the wistar species rats were weighed, and divided into two groups of fours. On the day of the manipulation, group one of our test animals received distilled water while the second group received 2000 mg/kg our dissolved powder.^[14]

We then observed the behavior of the animals in a period of 7days in the following interval; Day1: 1h-2h-4h-8h-16h-24h, where h stands for hour.

Day2-Day7.

During this time of observation, notes were taken on the following parameters: weight changes, behavioral changes, general wellbeing of the animal. Also if an animal died after the administration, the death should have been credited to the action of the substance according to OECD guidelines. Knowing from review that individual substances are not toxic, this test was carried out on the combination only.^[14]

II.2.4. Assessing the hypoglycemic property of powder

Following the toxicity test, it was time to proceed to the evaluation of the hypoglycemic property of the powder. We proceeded in the following manner:

Animals were raised by us, they received a rich and complete diet throughout the rearing process, with portable water and vitamins. Six rats divided into two groups, the first group served as negative control (distilled water). The other group was the testing group. The rats underwent the following treatment before testing;

The rats were randomly divided into 2 groups of threes. They were then exposed to 24hrs of fasting after which their fasting blood glucose levels were measured using IVD glucose meter. Following this, 40mg of powder dissolved in distilled water was given to one group through gavage, and the same volume of distilled water to the other group and the blood samples were collected from the tail vein at 0, 30, 60 and 90 min for glycemic control using IVD glucometer.^[15]

II.2.5. Assessing the anti-hyperglycemic control of powder

In this section, five groups of rats were used. The rats were treated the same way prior test as previously mentioned. After which they were given glucose (2 g/kg body weight) by gavage three different concentrations of the powder for the test groups (4 mg, 10 mg and 40 mg).^[16] Blood samples were collected from the tail vein at 0, 30, 60 and 90 min for glycemic control using IVD glucometer.^[17]

III.RESULTS

III.1. Observations made after acute toxicity test.

Table I: Results of Acute Toxicity Test.

Observations	Witness group	Test group 2000 mg/kg
Mucus secretion	Not occurred	Not occurred
Hair	N	N
Irritability	N	N
Salivation	N	N
Weight	N	N
Food water consumption	N	N
Eye colour	N	N
Sedation	Not observed	Not observed
Skin change	Normal	N
Urination	Normal	N
Convulsion	Not occurred	Not occurred
Coma	Not observed	Not observed
Lost of life	Alive	Alive

N: Normal

Figure 2: Evolution In The Weight Of Rats During Acute Toxicity Test.

After the administration of 2000 mg/kg of the powder to the rats according to the OECD guidelines for evaluating the acute toxicity of plant extract, the rats presented no sign of distress, no weight loss. After a period of more than two weeks the rats were healthy with no change in behavior and well being. The evolution in the weight of the animals in during a period of even days was normal without any significant difference between both group. These observations lead us to conclude that the powder combination was safe for use according to the OECD guidelines.

III.2. Assessing the Hypoglycemic Property Of Powder.

Figure 3: Result Of The Hypoglycemic Assessment Of Powder.

The difference in BGL between the two groups was highly significant as the p value at all points was far less than 0.05 as represented by the asterisk on the figure above. The lower curve indicates the glucose tolerance of the rats in the absence of the powder combination, while the higher line shows the same with the powder combination.

III.3. Evaluation of the effects of the combination on Glucose tolerance.

Figure 4: Comparison curve of the anti-hyperglycemic activities of the test groups.

This figure represents the different behaviors in the BGL of the rats after the administration of glucose at 2 g/kg followed by different substance which were: powder at three different concentrations, distilled water as negative control and glimepiride 2 as positive control. The Tukey's multiple comparisons test used in the column and row analysis, showed:

No significant difference in the blood glucose levels of the different groups at T0;

Significant differences at four different points at T30 between; 1. the group that took distilled water (A) and the group that took the powder at 10mg (D) with p value 0.0459, 2.the group that was given glimepiride 2 (B) and D with p value 0.0003, 3. Group B and the group that given powder at 40mg (E) with p value 0.0034, 4.group D and E with p value 0.0008.

Significant differences at five different places at T60, between; 1.group A and group with p value 0.0023, 2.group A and the group that was given powder at 4mg(C) with p value 0.0327, 3.group B and group C with p value 0.0006, 4.group B and group D with p value 0.0019, 5.group B and group E with p value 0.0002.

Significant differences at seven different points at T90 between; 1.group A and B with p value 0.451, 2.group A and D with p value 0.0163, 3.group A and E with p value 0.0262, 4.group B and D with p value 0.0086, 5.group B and E with p value 0.0294, 6.group C and D with p value 0.0054 and 7.group C and E with p value 0.0319.

IV. DISCUSSION

The primary objective of our research was to study the hypoglycemic and anti-hyperglycemic properties of a tri therapy powder obtained from combining *Allium sativum*, *Zingiber officinale* and *Hibiscus rosa sinensi* on the basis of the average of their active doses from different reviews. The difference in BGL during the hypoglycemic property study between the two groups was highly significant as the p value at all points was far less than 0.05 as represented by the asterisk (figure). The lower curve indicates the glucose tolerance of the rats in the absence of the powder combination, while the higher line shows the same with the powder combination. The group of rats that were given distilled water after 24hr fasting, shows lower values of glucose with time, meanwhile that which took the powder combination after oral glucose had their blood glucose levels alternating within the normal range, slightly above those of the first group. This then brings us to the conclusion that the powder combination poses no threat of causing hypoglycemia thus a potential candidate for glyceemic

control with little or no risk of causing hypoglycemia. This is different from the findings of Ansari et al on one of the component of the powder (hibiscus leaves) which showed a significant hypoglycemic property.

Tukey's multiple comparisons test used in the column and row analysis of the BGL of the rats after the administration of glucose at 2g/kg followed by different substance which were: powder at three different concentrations, distilled water as negative control and glimepiride 2 as positive control revealed glimepiride 2 to be the most active as it brought glyceic levels to very low values relative to the other groups. Amongst the test groups, it can be said that the concentration at 40mg was the most effective backing with the results in figure 6, this concentration maintained glucose levels within the normal range unlike 4mg and 10mg whose curves showed distinguishing high peaks of glucose levels at the same T 30.

Following the difference in the results, it is clear that the group of rats that were given glimepiride 2 tolerated glucose best, followed by group that was given distilled water. Following is the group that received the powder combination at 40mg. The other groups that were given powder at 4mg and 10mg showed high peaks of blood glucose at T30 compared to the others (figure6). We can thus say from the observations that the powder was unable to improve glucose tolerance in mice at lower doses (4 mg and 10 mg) but was able to improve the same slightly at the dose of 40mg. This brings us to the conclusion that the anti-hyperglycemic effect of the combination is dose dependent and therefore better results could be obtained at higher doses. Glimepiride 2 (positive control) had the best anti-hyperglycemic property compared to the combination. This is in line with the results on Al Mamun et al where metformine showed a better glyceic control than hibiscus leaves powder at low concentrations of powder.

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